

Development of a Digital Based Business Communication Network to Form an Entrepreneurial Ecosystem for Micro Small and Medium Enterprises

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to find answers to the research problem posed, The digital-based business communication network that is currently experienced by Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia is not yet optimal, where in addition to mentoring and mentoring, they also need aggregator business partners such as collaboration hubs or entrepreneurial ecosystems from various parties, both from the government, the business world and industry, academia, investor networks and the digital business community. Data were collected using a questionnaire containing questions related to research. Furthermore, in this study a theoretical model was developed by proposing 3 hypotheses to be tested using Structural Equations Modeling (SEM) using AMOS software. The results showed that, (1) digital-based business communication networks greatly affect the level of business sustainability that must be developed and implied as an action in making contact with business colleagues/partners and organizations, and business communication networks are an alternative to using internal and external resources(2) It takes the design of a digital-based entrepreneurial ecosystem hub that is compatible with institutional arrangements in the community. In addition, persistence and continuity are needed in guiding Micro Small and Medium Enterprises.

Keywords: Business Communication, Network Society, Business Sustainability, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Micro Small and Medium Enterprises

I. Introduction

Conceptually, the goal to be achieved in this research is to build and examine the development of new theoretical model approaches, as an effort to analyze, study and develop digital-based business communication networks to create an entrepreneurial ecosystem in Indonesia by testing empirically and analyze the perspective of business communication, the theory of network society and the theory of

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diffusion of innovations, the theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), so that a proposed grand theoretical model can be built, so that it can contribute, implicate and become a role model for the development of digital-based business communication networks to create an ecosystem entrepreneurship In Indonesia that is more sustainable and inclusive by utilizing the role of digitization in the Small and Medium Enterprises sector to improve digital interconnection, inclusiveness, productivity and business sustainability (Kurniullah, 2020). Research on business communication and the development of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in recent decades has become an interesting topic and a major concern for researchers and practitioners in Indonesia. This was found by researchers, that there are about 5,590,000 search results regarding research interests with the topic of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises on the Google search engine. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises are indeed a crucial business group and a business sector that has enormous potential for economic development in Indonesia.

The problem that is the subject of this research is that the digital-based business communication network that is currently experienced by Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia is not optimal, where in addition to mentoring and mentoring, they also need aggregator business partners such as collaboration hubs or entrepreneurial ecosystems from various parties both from government, business and industry, academia, investor networks and the digital business community. In addition, based on the facts on the ground, most Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business actors in carrying out their business activities are still low in the use of technology digitization and business applications, on the other hand, many business actors in using technology are still conventionally based, especially in the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises community in Indonesia (Adawiyah, 2016). so that it can hamper productivity, global marketing network, digitalization of technology and new media applications to support their business and business continuity. Moreover, the development of the technological superstructure and digital communications infrastructure today is taking place at a speed and volume that was unimaginable, perhaps even five or ten years earlier (Amelia, Prasetyo and Maharani, 2017). The digital information revolution is currently available in abundance and can be accessed easily and quickly via the Internet, anytime and from anywhere (Djatna and Luthfiyanti, 2015). As if there are no longer limitations of space and time in communicating, seeking, and exchanging information. This new form of communication via the internet or digital is the beginning of the rise of the information society era into power, as seen in the digital economy (Isenberg, 2014). Digitalization and the rise of global economic platforms or what is commonly known as e-commerce are rapidly changing the way companies do business in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, therefore a strong Entrepreneurial Ecosystem is needed to manage this change.

This research is motivated, several studies related to digital-based business communication and the entrepreneurial ecosystem in SMEs such as (Isenberg, 2010), (McLean, 2013), (Isenberg, 2016), (Yanti *et al.*, 2018), (Purbasari, Muhyi; and Sukoco, 2020), and the concept of entrepreneurship proposed by (Röpke, 1998) and (Robins and Coulter, 2012)), has not disclosed business communication and entrepreneurial ecosystem on the sustainability of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business. Several empirical studies conducted in developing countries revealed that, some of the most critical challenges in building an entrepreneurial ecosystem, according to the interviewees, and these barriers have now been grouped according to three main challenges, namely: (1) Barriers within entrepreneurs which include: (a) lack of necessary knowledge (planning, accounting, administration, finance, competitive culture, and lack of familiarity with the services provided), (b) lack of confidence, (c) lack of

work skills, (d) reluctance to accept concepts. (2) Institutional barriers include: (a) lack of support services (no clear procedure map, lengthy process, reluctance to implement one-stop service with clear procedures, and no updates with new activities), (b) weak regulations and administration. And (3) Financial and market barriers include: (a) guarantees provided to funding institutions, (b) networks, (c) funding policies and insurance terms, (d) finding customers or suppliers, (e) monopolies (hidden trading). Although the terms business communication and entrepreneurial ecosystem have been popular but there are still many opinions and theories compiled by researchers and practitioners that make there is no mutual acceptance of their definition, some practitioners and researchers see the business communication ecosystem as a facilitator where actors interact and work to a new result (Malecki, 2012). Another explanation of the ecosystem related to entrepreneurship is also given by Stam et al in their paper which explains that an ecosystem in entrepreneurship is an outcome related to performance in the economic system. This is based on the basis of the existence of an ecosystem, which is an activity that has economic objectives because it will produce inputs, outputs and outcomes among actors in the ecosystem. The entrepreneurial ecosystem is a relatively new concept, which has several definitions and no common definition. The concept of an entrepreneurial ecosystem in this study emphasizes how entrepreneurship is made possible by a comprehensive set of resources and actors that have an important role to play in all entrepreneurial actions. This study also uses the concepts and theories of network society, the diffusion of innovation theory and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory proposed by (Rogers, 1995), (Davis, 1989), (Spencer Lyle M, 1993), (Castells and Elgar, 2004) (Gottdiener, 2007), (van Dijk *et al.*, 2018). The emphasis on business networks and the use of new technology is focused on developing the ability of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business actors to take advantage of the adoption of new technologies and media in their business activities (Sawant Dessai, 2018). However, these statements are still abstract and have not been justified by empirical studies that use integrated and comprehensive indicators in measuring the ability of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business actors to take advantage of the adoption of new technology and media in their business activities.

The novelty and contribution of the results of this research is to identify in detail and describe theoretically as well as abstracting into new constructs in the context of the Integrated Model for Development of Digital-Based Business Communication Networks to Realize the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia which refers to the principles of ontology, epistemology and axiology. so that it can be proposed as a difference or novelty construct referring to the perspective of the previous literature, or reconstructing to contribute theoretically, to: the cybernetic tradition of communication science, business communication theory, business networking, level of business sustainability, entrepreneurial ecosystem, network society theory, diffusion theory innovation and technology acceptance model (TAM) theory. Conceptually, it is identifying the application of digital-based business communication networks in the cybernetics tradition of communication science, theoretically i.e. collaborating and elaborating theoretically on business communication, business networks, business sustainability, entrepreneurial ecosystem, society network theory, innovation diffusion theory and technology acceptance model (TAM) theory can confirm the terminology building of business communication theory which has been limited so far by citing management theory that tends to be purely economic purposes, empirically by utilizing primary data of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business actors in business mapping and description of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors profiles, Mapping of obstacles faced and the inclusion of communication aspects In practical terms, namely as a development model to create an integrated, inclusive and sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem for Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors to

support macroeconomic growth that is pro-people and pro Micro Small and Medium Enterprises are compiled by involving the opinions of experts and policy makers.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis

2.1 Concept of Digital-Based Business Communication Network and Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

The existence of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in the context of economic development occupies a central position to reduce the possibility of volatility in the elements forming gross domestic income through employment and increasing the volume of activities that encourage consumption growth and investment in the real sector. Data from the 2016 Economic Census conducted by the Central Statistics Agency, there were 26.71 million business units that fall into the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises category in Indonesia (LPPI, 2015). Of the number of business actors in this category, the contribution to GDP is 61.41% or IDR. 6,228 trillion by absorbing 96.7% of the total workforce. Meanwhile, in terms of investment contributions, Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors contributed 56.2% of the total national investment (Suci, 2017). A number of "classic" factors that have been suspected to be obstacles in efforts to develop competitiveness and resilience include: mastery of technology and innovation, human capital capacity, compliance with legal aspects, access to funding sources and markets, and financial resources. creations for product development and excellent service. All of them are classic issues that continue to require integrated handling efforts, both from the technical management of the organization and at the level of public policy. Apart from the limitations inherent in the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises group, the current macro situation and conditions indicate that there are gaps and development potentials that are still open to accelerate productive economic growth by relying on information technology-based innovation (Lantu *et al.*, 2016). In addition, communication has a very important role in the potential for developing Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in managing business in the digital era, namely an era where information is crowded which must require every individual to create ideas, productivity and creativity innovations in order to be able to compete in today's modern business life. Business communication consists of two syllables, namely communication and business. Where communication is a basic human activity. By communicating, humans can relate to each other both in everyday life in the household, at work, in the market, in society or wherever humans are. There is no human being who will not engage in communication (Tyler, 1993).

As stated above, communication is one of the management functions of business organizations. Therefore, communication will exist and continue to take place in an organization as long as the organization exists. Herein lies the importance of making a business communication plan so that business communication can run effectively. The concept of a digital-based business communication network that was developed and implied in this study is an act of making contact with business colleagues/partners and organizations, and a business communication network is an alternative to using internal and external resources. Business communication networks are variables that are considered important for all types of companies, especially with regard to the fact that the business environment in the digital era is becoming increasingly competitive and disruptive. Digital-based business communication networks are becoming increasingly important because they make it easier for companies to access information, resources, markets and technology (Gulati, Nohria and Zaheer, 2000). Information and social networks are considered important for the formation of companies and for the

success and sustainability of companies (Malecki, 2012). Digital-based business communication networks are often defined as patterned relationships among stakeholders. Business communication networks can take various forms including: strategic alliances, joint ventures, licensing arrangements, and subcontracting, joint R & D and marketing activities. Various definitions of networks have been raised by scientists but the most widely used concept is the concept of (Hoang and Antoncic, 2003) which describes a network as a set of actors (nodes) and a set of relationships (links) that relate these actors. In using the relational concept, please note that the actors and their actions are considered interdependent rather than independent, the relational ties between the actors are a channel or a place for the flow of resources (Scott *et al.*, 1996). The existence of inter-relationship conditions becomes a basis for the formation of networks related to the market. The network is a pattern of a minimum of two reciprocal relationships between companies that establish certain collaborations (Rudawska, 2020).

In this study, the researchers put forward the establishment of a Digital-Based Business Communication Network by using the concept of social networking and business communication formed through digital technology which is a liaison/hub in the development of information flow between network groups that are connected in the network society group. Social and communication networks have a very important role in business management in the digital era, namely an era where information is crowded which requires every individual to create ideas, innovation, productivity and creativity in order to be able to compete in today's modern business life (Ahmad and Dimitratos, 2017). Business communication consists of two syllables, namely communication and business. Where communication is a basic human activity. In addition, the entrepreneurial ecosystem approach contains a set of actors and factors that are related and coordinated both formally and informally that are interconnected with each other, mutually regulate and mediate all entrepreneurial performance starting from the initial stages that give birth to new entrepreneurs to business development that aims to increase the number of entrepreneurs in the industry (Tuta and Ordonez, 2016). increase ability and competitiveness (Purbasari, Muhyi; and Sukoco;, 2020). So far, the entrepreneurial ecosystem is a relatively new concept, which has several definitions and no common definition. The concept of an entrepreneurial ecosystem emphasizes how entrepreneurship is made possible by a comprehensive set of resources and actors who have an important role to play in all entrepreneurial actions. In general, the entrepreneurial ecosystem is composed of easy market access, human resources, capital and financing, supporting networks (mentors, consultants, incubators, entrepreneurial networks), policies and regulations, training and socialization, availability of educational institutions, and factor support. socio-cultural (Isenberg, 2014). The model of the entrepreneurial ecosystem actually emphasizes the linkages between actors to be able to produce productive entrepreneurship and give birth to new entrepreneurs (Stam and Spigel, 2007).

2.2 Theoretical and hypotheses

Discussing the technological paradigm, there are several things that characterize the new paradigm of technology. The first character: information is the raw material. Here, technology acts in the form of information, not just information acting on technology. Second character: The effects of new technology are pervasive. This is carried away by the fact that information is an integral part of human activity, so all personal and group processes are shaped by new technologies. While the third character: network logic is the basis for various systems and relationships that use this new information technology. The morphology of this network adds to the complexity of the interaction and the uncertainty of the form of development that arises from the interaction itself. The fourth character: flexibility. All organizational and institutional components can be merged and modified, by rearranging

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the components they have. What distinguishes the configuration of this new technological paradigm, is its ability to reconfigure a society through existing changes (Stark and Castells, 1997). The network was formed not only to communicate but also to achieve a position that is more than just communicating. This happens because flexibility has the ability as well as a 'coercive'. The fifth character: the growth of technology convergence that is specific to the system, which is well integrated. Thus, what was discussed earlier regarding micro-electronics, telecommunications, opto-electronics and computers, are all integrated into an information system. Once present, will always be present. It can be concluded that the information technology paradigm is not only seen as a system, but rather as a network openness. This is something that is strong, but adaptive and open in its historical development. The social dimension of the information technology revolution, in synergy following the law of the relationship between technology and society.

According to (Castells and Elgar, 2004), society lives in a new order with 3 main characters: informational, global and networked. It is called informational because the productivity and competitiveness of a unit or agency: company, region or country, in an economic system, fundamentally depends on its ability to generate, process and apply knowledge based on information efficiently (Handarkho *et al.*, 2017). Called global, because the main activities of production, consumption and circulation, including the components that affect it: capital, labor, raw materials, management, information, technology and markets, are organized on a global scale, directly or through related networks among agents. economy. While it is called networked, because in this new historical condition, productivity is generated through competition that is played in a global network that interacts with each other among business people. The three characteristics above cannot be separated from the role of information technology since its birth and its very rapid spread. Furthermore, according to him, the new economy, society and culture is a necessary condition. Social network is one of the dimensions of social capital in addition to trust and norms. The concept of network in social capital focuses more on aspects of the ties between nodes which can be in the form of people or groups (organizations) (Adawiyah, 2016). In this case, there is an understanding of the existence of social relations that are bound by the existence of trust in which trust is maintained and maintained by existing norms. In this network concept, there is an element of work, which through the media of social relations becomes cooperation. Basically social networks are formed because of mutual knowledge, mutual information, reminding each other, and helping each other in implementing or overcoming something. In essence, the concept of network in social capital refers to all relationships with other people or groups that allow activities to run efficiently and effectively (Blackburn, De Clercq and Heinonen, 2017).

In addition to the perspective of network society theory, researchers are also interested in using (Rogers, Singhal and Quinlan, 2019) perspective on the characteristics of innovation to help explain the extent to which the adoption of new media and digital technology can bring implications in developing the entrepreneurial ecosystem of SMEs in Indonesia based on digital applications. The diffusion of innovation consists of two equivalent words, namely diffusion and innovation. (Rogers, 1995) defines diffusion as the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over a period of time among the members of a social system. If an innovation has a relative advantage, is in accordance with previous values and habits, is uncomplicated, can be tested, and can be observed, then the innovation will be quickly adopted by individuals or social systems. In addition, in this study, researchers used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The researcher uses the Technology

Acceptance Model (TAM) theory developed by (Davis, 1989) to explain the behavior intention of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in developing business communication networks in the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises ecosystem in Indonesia based on digital applications.

Based on the theoretical description, the hypo theses used in this study areas following:

H1: There is a real influence between digital-based business communication networks on the level of operations management for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.

H2: There is a significant influence between the level of operations management on the formation of an entrepreneurial ecosystem for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.

H3: There is a real influence between digital-based business communication networks on the formation of an entrepreneurial ecosystem for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia.

3. Research Methods

This research uses a mixed method or often referred to as a mixed method. The implementation of this mixed methods research combines quantitative and qualitative research methods. As for this type of mixed research using a sequential explanatory strategy. The research location in this dissertation was carried out in Indonesia. Data collection was carried out from September 2020 to February 2021. The sampling method based on the type of business used in this study was non-proportionate stratified random sampling. The population in this study are Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors in regencies/cities in DKI Jakarta, including the Kepulauan Seribu, South Jakarta, East Jakarta, Central Jakarta, West Jakarta and North Jakarta. Based on the Slovin formula, a total sample of 400 respondents was obtained with an error rate of 5 percent.

The validity test in this study was carried out by calculating the corrected item to total correlation, namely by correlating the score of each item with the total score. The results of the validity test show that the corrected item total correlation value of the overall indicator items from the 3 variables tested in this study is declared valid and can be used in the next analysis. Testing the reliability of the questionnaire in this study using the cronbach alpha coefficient. The results of there liability test show that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha coefficient valuea bove 0.6, so the scale used in this study can be said to be reliable and able to provid econsistent measurement results. The data is said to be normal if the multi variate critical ratio has a condition of -2.58 critical ratio 2.58 . Based on the results of the normality test, it is known that the critical value of the multivariate ratio is 4.334 whosevalueis not in the range of -2.58 to 2.58 , so it can be concluded that the assumption of multivariate normality has not beenmet. However, based on the Central Limit Theorm which states that if n (sample size) is large ($n > 30$), then the statistics of the sample will approach the normal distribution even though the sample is taken from an abnormal population. So based on this argument, the assumption of normality can be fulfilled. Technical analysis of the data used in this study includes quantitative analysis and qualitativ eanalysis. The quantitative data analysis techniqueuses descriptive statistical analysis, correlation analysis, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) which is operated through the Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 21.0 program, difference test analysis and hypothesis testing. While the qualitative data analysis uses internal validity (credibility), external validity (transferability), reliability (dependability) and objectivity (confirmability). Internal validity is done in the form of credibility (trust).

4. Results

Research on the Development of Digital-Based Business Communication Networks to Realize the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia was carried out by distributing questionnaires conducted from 1 December 2020 to 25 May 2021 with a total of 400 respondents. After identifying the characteristic profile of the respondents based on the demographic factors that have been described regarding the description of the research object above, then in the description of the results of this study it is determined how far the role of digital-based business communication networks in the entrepreneurial ecosystem with business sustainability as an intermediate variable. After the primary data has been collected through the distribution of questionnaires, then the data filtering process is carried out according to the characteristics of the sample that have been determined through tabulation. Then, data analysis was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Analysis technique which was operated through the Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) 21.0 program. And using the computer program SPSS (Statistics Program for Social Science) for Windows 26.0. Validity tests have been carried out to determine whether the measuring instruments compiled can be used to measure what is intended to be measured accurately. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the questionnaire questions are able to measure what is desired. In other words, able to obtain the right data from the variables studied (Taylor et al., 2010). The validity test in this study was carried out by calculating the corrected item to total correlation, namely by correlating the score of each item with the total score. According to (Solimun, 2008) an item is said to be valid if the correlation value is positive and > 0.3 then the indicator is considered valid. The results of the validity test can be explained in the following table:

Tabel 1
Results of Testing the Validity of the Questionnaire Instruments

Indikator	CIT <i>Correlation</i>	r standa r	Informatio n
Digital-Based Business Communication Network(X)	0,335	0,3	Valid
X2_1	0,522	0,3	Valid
X2_2	0,538	0,3	Valid
X2_3	0,391	0,3	Valid
X2_4	0,463	0,3	Valid
X2_5	0,467	0,3	Valid
X2_6	0,476	0,3	Valid
X2_7	0,566	0,3	Valid
X2_8	0,529	0,3	Valid
X2_9	0,542	0,3	Valid
X2_10	0,568	0,3	Valid
X2_11	0,489	0,3	Valid
X3_1	0,305	0,3	Valid

X3_2	0,393	0,3	Valid
X3_3	0,400	0,3	Valid
X3_4	0,408	0,3	Valid
X4_1	0,417	0,3	Valid
X4_2	0,387	0,3	Valid
X4_3	0,430	0,3	Valid
X4_4	0,551	0,3	Valid
X4_5	0,530	0,3	Valid
X5_1	0,481	0,3	Valid
X5_2	0,542	0,3	Valid
X5_3	0,568	0,3	Valid
X5_4			
Operations management (Z)			
Z1_1	0,313	0,3	Valid
Z1_2	0,481	0,3	Valid
Z1_3	0,440	0,3	Valid
Z1_4	0,484	0,3	Valid
Z1_5	0,515	0,3	Valid
Z2_1	0,528	0,3	Valid
Z2_2	0,466	0,3	Valid
Z2_3	0,597	0,3	Valid
Z2_4	0,518	0,3	Valid
Z3_1	0,445	0,3	Valid
Z3_2	0,572	0,3	Valid
Z3_3	0,548	0,3	Valid
Z3_4	0,537	0,3	Valid
Z3_5	0,448	0,3	Valid
Z4_1	0,539	0,3	Valid
Z4_2	0,626	0,3	Valid
Z4_3	0,425	0,3	Valid
Z4_4	0,456	0,3	Valid
Z4_5	0,497	0,3	Valid
Z4_6	0,460	0,3	Valid
Entrepreneurial Ecosystem(Y)			
Y1			
Y2	0,672	0,3	Valid
Y3	0,703	0,3	Valid
Y4	0,624	0,3	Valid
Y5	0,715	0,3	Valid
Y6	0,678	0,3	Valid
Y7	0,654	0,3	Valid
	0,697	0,3	Valid

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Based on table 1 the results of the validity test above, it shows that the corrected item total correlation value of the overall indicator items from the 3 variables tested in this study is declared valid and can be used in the next analysis. The reliability test was conducted to show that the questionnaire used was reliable, that is, if it was tested repeatedly on the same group, it would produce the same data (Solimun, 2008). Testing the reliability of the questionnaire in this study used the Cronbach alpha coefficient. According to (O’Cathain, 2019), if the Cronbach alpha coefficient is 0.6 or less, it generally indicates an unsatisfactory internal consistency reliability. It can be concluded where a variable is said to be reliable if the Cronbach alpha value > 0.6. The results of the reliability test are described in the following table:

Tabel2

Results of Testing the Reliability of the Questionnaire Instruments

Variabel	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	Reference Value	Information
Digital-Based Business Communication Network(X)	0,853	0.6	Reliabel
Operations management (Z)	0,884	0.6	Reliabel
Entrepreneurial Ecosystem(Y)	0,843	0.6	Reliabel

Based on table 2 of their liability test results above, it shows that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha coefficient value above 0.6, so the scale used in this study can be said to be reliable and able to provide consistent measurement results. The data is said to be normal if the multivariate critical ratio has a condition of -2.58 critical ratio 2.58 . If the data is not normal, it is necessary to clean the outlier data so that the data becomes normal (Taylor *et al.*, 2010). Based on the Central Limit Theorem, that is, if n (sample size) is large ($n > 30$), then the statistics of the sample will approach a normal distribution, even though the population from which the sample is taken is not normally distributed (Solimun, 2008). The following are the results of the multivariate normality test which can be seen in the following table:

Tabel3

Results of Testing the Normality of the Questionnaire Instruments

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
Y7	1.000	5.000	-.839	-.847	.912	.805
Y6	2.000	5.000	-.898	-1.335	.827	1.460
Y5	1.000	5.000	-.745	-1.079	1.614	.590
Y4	1.000	5.000	-.994	-2.119	1.504	1.223
Y3	1.000	5.000	-1.004	-.202	1.313	.608
Y2	1.000	5.000	-1.222	-.974	1.520	1.289
Y1	1.000	5.000	-.275	-.414	.881	.845
Z4_Rata	1.000	5.000	-1.262	-.308	1.443	1.055
Z3_Rata	1.000	5.000	-.767	-.714	.189	.220
Z2_Rata	1.000	5.000	-.287	-.688	.276	.374
Z1_Rata	1.000	5.000	-1.190	-.717	.305	1.577
X5_Rata	1.000	5.000	-.129	-.220	.688	2.057

Variable	min	max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
X4_Rata	1.000	5.000	-.638	-.205	.948	0.869
X3_Rata	1.000	5.000	-.507	-1.137	.869	1.547
X2_Rata	2.000	5.000	-.733	-.981	.810	.308
X1_Rata	2.000	5.000	-.684	-1.584	.391	1.681
Multivariate					5.301	4.334

Based on table 3, it is known that the critical value of the multivariate ratio is 4.334 whose value is not in the range of -2.58 to 2.58, so it can be concluded that the assumption of multivariate normality has not been met. However, based on the Central Limit Theorem which states that if n (sample size) is large ($n > 30$), then the statistics of the sample will approach the normal distribution even though the sample is taken from an abnormal population. So based on this argument, the assumption of normality can be fulfilled. The step that must be taken before assessing the feasibility of the structural model is to assess the goodness of fit. The goodness of fit test for the structural model can be seen in Figure 1 The results of the structural model estimation using the Maximum Likelihood estimation method can be seen in table 4.86. The calculation results show that there are 3 index criteria that do not meet the model fit assumption, namely the Probability Level index, AGFI and RMSEA. Referring to the opinion of (Solimun, 2008) which states that based on the parsimony rule, if one or two of the fit criteria of the model have been met, the model has been declared fit. From these various conformity indices, it can be concluded that the structural model in the proposed endogenous construct is fit or has a good suitability so that there is no need for interpretation and modification of the model.

Fig. 1. Full Model Confirmatory Analysis

Based on the estimation results of the structural model using the Maximum Likelihood estimation method, the following values are obtained:

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Tabel4

Model Feasibility Test Results (Full Model)

Goodness of Fit Measure	Index	Reference Value	Information
Chi-square of estimate model (df = 101)	745,816		
Probability Level	0,000	> 0,05	Not fit
Cmindf	7,384	< 2	Not fit
GFI	0,905	> 0,9	Good Fit
AGFI	0,937	≥ 0,9	Marginal
RMSEA	0,096	0,05 - 0,08	Not fit
RMR	0,047	≤ 0,05	Good Fit
TLI	0,966	≥ 0,9	Good Fit
CFI	0,973	≥ 0,9	Good Fit
NFI	0,981	≥ 0,9	Good Fit

Hypothesis testing is done by comparing the probability of significance (p) with the level of significance (α) that has been determined previously, which is 0.05. If the comparison of the significance probability value (p) is smaller than the significance level (α), then the proposed hypothesis can be accepted, where as if the significance probability value (p) is greater than the significance level value (α), then the hypothesis is rejected. The following are the results of the SEM test with the SEM coefficient value or the standardize coefficient for each variable.

Tabel5

Hypothesis Conclusion

Hypothesis		Estimate	C.R	p
H1	Operations management ← Digital-Based Business Communication Network	.780	7.441	***
H2	Operations management ← Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	.162	3.649	***
H3	Entrepreneurial Ecosystem ← Digital-Based Business Communication Network	.799	7.849	***

Based on Table 5, the results of the second hypothesis test obtained a significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) and a C.R value of 7,441, this value is greater than 1.96. So the second hypothesis states that there is a real influence between digital-based business communication networks on the level of business sustainability for micro, small and medium enterprises. Meanwhile, for the third hypothesis test results obtained a significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) and a C.R value of 3.649, this value is greater than 1.96. So , the third hypothesis which states that there is a real influence between the level of business sustainability on the formation of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of micro, small and medium enterprises. The results of the fourth hypothesis test obtained a significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) and a C.R value of 7.849, this value is greater than 1.96. So the fourth hypothesis which states that there is a real influences between digital-based business communications networks on the formation of the

entrepreneurial ecosystem of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors in Indonesia. After testing the hypothesis, the next step is to determine which variable relationship is the most influential. To find out which variable relationship has the most influence, it can be seen from the magnitude of the estimate value, namely the digital-based business communication network on the formation of an entrepreneurial ecosystem for Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia of 0.799.

5. Conclusion

This study purposed to answer the formulation of the problem and research questions that have been proposed, therefore, the conclusions obtained from this dissertation are: (1) digital-based business communication networks greatly affect the level of business sustainability that must be developed and implied as an action in carrying out contacts with business colleagues/partners as well as organizations, and business communication networks are an alternative to using internal and external resources. (2) There is a positive and significant influence between the level of business sustainability on the formation of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. a digital-based entrepreneurial ecosystem hub design is needed that is compatible with institutional arrangements in the community. In addition, persistence and continuity are needed in guiding Micro Small and Medium Enterprises. Not merely setting a solution, but stimulating the emergence of solutions from existing social capital. (3) An integrated model of digital-based business communication network as a determinant of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, namely through building a consolidated business network (networking), designing business communication strategies, designing an enabler platform for integrated Micro Small and Medium Enterprises business continuity, technology intermediaries, hyper connectivity and visibility of the synchronization of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises data information flows and formed the Indonesian Center of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (In CoME). The limitations of this study, the scope of this study is limited to data obtained based on the survey method through filling out questionnaires to Micro Small and Medium Enterprises actors in the Indonesia, so there is the possibility of biased data, for example due to respondents filling out questionnaires carelessly or filling out incorrectly. Honest. For this reason, it is recommended that further research replicates the framework of this research, methodologically using either quantitative or qualitative methods within the scope of the National Scale. Based on the data from the research, it can be suggested that there is a need for synergy from all parties, including the government, creative actors, and corporations/private sectors to work on business communication networks, internationalization and absorption of technology into the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The development of information technology that is integrated with various creative ideas about Micro Small and Medium Enterprises will allow every business to be able to move according to the needs of the community, solve social problems, and have a wider impact.

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Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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